

The main trend in the labor markets of both developed and developing countries.

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Annotation. The article analyzes the current global economic and technological trends affecting the transformation of the labor market and the formation of new socio-economic relations in the context of the formation of the digital economy. The author draws attention to the changes in the nature of labor and forms of labor activity, the requirements for professional skills and abilities. It is shown how the changes associated with the digitalization of the economy directly affect the issues of training and retraining of the most in-demand specialists.

Keywords: labor relations; labor market; digital economy; robotization; artificial intelligence; personnel development; creation of new jobs; training; retraining

Introduction. The development of the digital economy, based on the production, distribution and consumption of information, causes major socio-economic shifts, including in the field of labor relations, while the type of professional activity and the nature of the work itself are changing. In the digital economy, the accumulation of material wealth ceases to be the main goal of society, intangible values and interests come to the fore.

The new nature of work is associated with the improvement of the qualifications of employees, their constant training and creative communication. The development of the labor market based on digital technologies leads to the modernization of labor relations: in communication between employers and performers, there is an active use of information and communication technologies (hereinafter referred to as ICT) and the formation of new norms of behavior.

Until now, the domestic labor market has remained largely unchanged under the influence of digital technologies, but the accelerating digitalization of the economy poses new challenges for industries and the state that they have not faced before.

The problems of employment in the digital economy are taking on a new meaning. Human and social capital are considered as key sources of wealth, which requires a conceptual shift in people's minds from the position of "profit maximization" to the position of "utility maximization".

Thus, the period of the emergence of the digital economy requires a quick response to changes in the labor market, investments in human capital and new ways to improve it, adapt to new conditions, and program measures on the part of the state.

Changing the nature and type of labor relations in the digital economy. One of the most common types of employment relationships in the digital economy is to work from home instead of moving to the office for the duration of the working day. In addition, the following types of work have appeared: during vacation (on a train, on a plane, in a hotel), for a foreign employer without going abroad (for example, the work of offshore programmers), etc.

The development of labor relations in the digital economy leads to the replacement of permanent staff with temporary performers, while many types of work can be performed thousands of kilometers from the office and even beyond national borders. A noticeable trend in recent years has been a very rapid increase in the number of freelance employees. For example, in the United States alone in 2017, there were 57.3 million people working in freelance mode (including part-time), which is 36% of the working population of the country ¹.

As a result, the new employment relationship contributes to:

- a significant reduction in transaction costs (office rent, recruitment, transportation costs);
- the introduction of flexible work organization and flexible staff;
- increase in labor productivity (by eliminating obstacles to work that exist in the office);
- increasing motivation (increasing trust between the employer and the employee); – improved customer service (around the clock, without overtime pay).

In the digital economy, not only the nature of work is changing, but also the entire system of labor relations. If in the traditional economy there are vertical economic ties of management / subordination between the employee and the employer, then in the digital sector, the manager is no longer so much a boss as a person who coordinates the work of people who are sometimes at a

¹ Horowitz S. Freelancing in America 2017. Freelancers Union. Available at: <https://blog.freelancersunion.org/2017/10/17/freelancing-in-america-2017/> (accessed: 04.11.2018).

great distance from each other. Accordingly, vertical ties are replaced by horizontal ones, while the dependence of the employee on the head of the company is significantly weakened.

An increase in the independence of the employee forms a special kind of partnership between him and the manager, which requires a corresponding increase in trust. The specialist himself forms a portfolio of orders, agrees on the volume and timing of work, as well as the amount of his own remuneration. The qualification and authority of the contractor provide him with constant replenishment of the portfolio of orders. Therefore, there is inevitably a rejection of the philosophy of "one job for life" and a desire to independently form a portfolio of work and manage it. It is also important that digital employment provides new opportunities for both residents of cities and residents of the "provinces": workers who used to have to move from the provinces to the capital to be present in the central office can now live in any locality with access to the Internet. Thus, employment in the digital sphere provides an individual with numerous advantages (Fig. 1).

In the digital economy, completely new skills and competencies are required. In order to leverage digital technologies and scale up nationally and internationally, organizations need employees with the right mix of technical, business, interpersonal, and creative skills. In today's conditions, basic skills (the ability to write correctly, count, etc.) are clearly no longer enough – it is also necessary to have business and interpersonal qualities. Critical to any production process or service delivery are modern technical skills, complemented by leadership level skills (C-suite, entrepreneurial) specifically adapted for digital management.

For employers, the so-called "soft skills" of potential candidates have recently become a priority: personal qualities and social skills, for example, the ability to work in a team, curiosity, initiative, critical thinking, self-management, the ability to solve complex problems, interact with different people, and set priorities correctly.

At the same time, as noted by some heads of large organizations, the role of formal diplomas and educational certificates has significantly decreased. Top companies such as Google, Apple, and IBM, as well as the international consulting giant Ernst & Young, do not require higher education diplomas when applying for a job — relevant experience is enough. But this is not always mandatory.

Results and Analyses

Today, the industrial sector employs 320 million workers worldwide and only 2.1 million robots (Figure 2). According to ABI Research, the market for manufacturing robots will grow by 16% per year, and by 2025, the level of shipments will triple.

Despite the tremendous growth in factory automation, the density of industrial robots varies by region. On average, in 2015, the density was 66 units per 10,000 workers, and by the end of 2017 it had increased to 74. Individually, we see an uneven picture: in the EU countries, this figure is 99, in Asia – 63, in South and North America – 84.² Robotization reached its maximum in 2010–2016: the average annual growth rate reached 9% in Asia, 7% in South and North America, and 5% in Europe.

The top ten most robotic countries in the world in 2017 included Belgium, Denmark, Germany, Italy, Japan, Singapore, the United States, Taiwan, Sweden, South Korea and Japan. The fastest development of robotization of production is in China. Now the country ranks 23rd in the ranking, but by 2020 it should enter the top ten with 150 robots per 10,000 personnel. In 2017, there were 630 industrial robots per 10,000 workers in South Korea, mainly engaged in the production of electronics and cars. Japan is the world leader in the production of industrial robots: the country provides 52% of the world market. In 2016, Japanese enterprises produced 153K industrial robots, which is a record number.³

² Statistics of the world density of industrial robots // MENTAMORE. – Rezhim dostupa: <https://mentamore.com/robototexnika/statistika-mirovoj-plotnosti-promyshlennyx-robotov.html>. Accessed on 05.11.2018.

³ Robot density rises globally: IFR Press Release, Frankfurt, Feb 07, 2018 // International Federation of Robotics. – Mode of Access: <https://ifr.org/ifr-press-releases/news/robot-density-rises-globally>. – Date of access: 05.11.2018.

List of employees carrying out research and development

Fig. 2. The list number of employees performing research and development Note. Developed on the basis of .⁴

Robots are vastly superior to humans in endurance, accuracy, and speed. In other words, they are more productive and have little to no scrap (if set up correctly). And this means that robotization, which increases productivity and reduces the cost of production, will generally be an unconditional benefit and a driver of economic development.

According to a report by the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development, robotization will be the first to take two-thirds of jobs from residents of developing countries, including Ethiopia, Nepal, Cambodia, China and Bangladesh.⁵ By 2024, robots will put one in four people in Russia unemployed (according to the recruiting portal Superjob), by 2025 - 7% of Americans (Forrester Research report), by 2026 - 40% of Canadians (report by the Brookfield Institute for Innovation and Entrepreneurship), and by 2035 they will occupy half of jobs in Japan (report by the Nomura Research Institute).

⁴ Statistics of the world density of industrial robots // MENTAMORE. – Rezhim dostupa: <https://mentamore.com/robototexnika/statistika-mirovoj-plotnosti-promyshlennyx-robotov.html>. Accessed on 05.11.2018.

⁵ UNCTAD Policy Brief: Robots and Industrialization // UNCTAD. – Mode of Access: https://unctad.org/en/PublicationsLibrary/presspb2016d6_en.pdf. – Date of access: 08.11.2018.

Table 1. Estimates of the impact of digital technology on employment

Organization	Predictive Assessment
OECD	OECD average: 9% of jobs at high risk of automation over the next five years. Low risk of full automation, but a significant proportion (50-70%) of automated tasks at risk
World Bank	Two-thirds of all jobs in developing countries are subject to automation
World Economic Forum	Global job losses by 2030 – from 2 million to 2 billion people
International Labour Organization	ASEAN 5: 56% of jobs at risk of automation in the next 20 years
University of Oxford	47% of workers in the U.S. are at high risk of replacing jobs with automation
Pricewaterhouse Coopers	38% of jobs in the US, 30% in the UK, 21% in Japan and 35% in Germany are at risk of automation
McKinsey	60% of all professions have at least 30% of technically automated activities
Roland Berger	Western Europe: By 2035, 8.3 million jobs will be lost in manufacturing, but 10 million new jobs will be created in services
Klaus Schwab	Eliminate about 5 million jobs in the world's 15 largest developed and developing countries by 2020

Note. Developed on the basis of ⁶.

By 2036, 2 to 50 percent of man-hour work could be automated, and by 2066, that share could reach 46 to 99 percent⁷. The World Economic Forum's The Future of Jobs Reports 2018

⁶ Inception Report for the Global Commission on the Future of Work. 2017 // International Labour Organization. – Mode of Access: https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---dgreports/---cabinet/documents/publication/wcms_591502.pdf. – Date of access: 06.11.2018

⁷ Aptekman, A. Digital Russia: New Reality. July 2017 / A. Aptekman [et al.]. – Moscow: McKinsey, 2017. – 133 p.

says that the proportion of human work in terms of man-hours will fall from 71 percent in 2018 to 48 percent by 2025.⁸ Machines and algorithms will increase their contribution to specific tasks by an average of 57%. For example, by 2022, 62% of information retrieval, processing, and communication tasks will be performed by machines, compared to 46% today.

Conclusion

The main trend in the labor markets of both developed and developing countries is the disappearance of professions that provide standardized services. Already today, automatic cash registers around the world are replacing cashiers, conductors in public transport are no longer needed. In any major city, you can find terminals with coffee and food, parking payment machines, etc.

If we look into the near future, machines will replace many professions, because the market economy and growing competition require enterprises and companies to constantly improve efficiency. As examples of disappearing professions, The Future of Jobs Reports 2018 cites the following: data entry operators, accountants and auditors, tax inspectors, postal workers, bank employees, financial analysts, sales agents and resellers, brokers, cashiers, assembly line workers, car and van drivers, shop assistants, statistician, financial and insurance specialists, lawyers.

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⁸ The Future of Jobs Reports 2018 // World Economic Forum. – Mode of Access: http://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_Future_of_Jobs_2018.pdf. – Date of access: 02.11.2018

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